

INFLUENCE OF OPTICAL FIBER SENSOR PLACEMENT ON CFRP LAMINATES FOR PROCESS AND STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING

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Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)

The use of polymer composites in aeronautics has been increasing in the last few decades to replace metallic structures. The use of composites can improve the mechanical performance by weight ratio, allowing to reduce fuel consumption, CO₂ emissions and, therefore costs [1]. Although composite materials hold promising achievements, their failure is still very difficult to predict [2].

Aeronautic composites are prone to barely visible impact damage (BVID), which may occur during manufacturing or maintenance operations, resulting from, for example, a drop of a hand tool, or in service due to heavy hail. This may produce transverse cracks, delaminations and fibre breakage that may go undetected during inspection operations [3]. The implementation of SHM systems is essential to ensure that such structures are intervened as needed upon damage, extending their lifetime in the harsh space environment they are exposed to [4]. SHM is a cost-effective approach that uses surface mounted or embedded sensors [1]

Adapted from [5]

Objectives

- Production of CFRP laminates with embedded FBG sensors by vacuum infusion
- Use of small diameter OF to minimize mechanical properties impairment produced by sensor embedding
- Optimization of OF location for improved damage detectability
- Use of FBG sensors for in-situ cure monitoring and detection of BVID produced by drop weight impact tests

Materials and Samples

Samples

4 mm thick quasi-isotropic [0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0]2s (32 layers)

OF Locations in z-axis

0/45/90/-45/ OF (C)/-45/90/45/0/OF (B)/0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0/OF (A)/0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0/0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0

- OF are placed parallel and between 2 consecutive fabric layers with the same ply orientation, aiming to minimize defects and least impaired mechanical properties of the composite
- Each sample has OF in one single location

OF Placement Evaluation

Top, side, front and 3-dimensional images taken by XCT at a specimen with OF on location A

Mechanical Testing

Tensile Testing

- Load cell: 100 kN
- Test velocity: 2 mm/min

Sample	E (GPa)	Ultimate strength (MPa)
NL	43.2 ± 3.2	322.2 ± 53.7
A	41.2 ± 1.6	318.7 ± 63.2
B	40.9 ± 1.7	429.0 ± 6.4
C	44.3 ± 1.7	377.4 ± 34.3

Figure: Example of tested tensile specimen with OF on location B
Table: Average values of Young's modulus, E, and ultimate strength for neat CFRP laminate and CFRP laminates with embedded OF on locations A, B and C

Impact Testing

(a) Example of impact energy for each OF location for impact energy events of 15.3 J and 20.3 J; Measured impactor contact force of: (b) damaged specimens exposed to an impact energy of 20.3 J; (c) specimens exposed to an impact energy of 15.3 J with visible impact damage on back surface; (d) specimens exposed to an impact energy of 15.3 J without visible impact damage on back surface

Cure Monitoring

Wavelength variation of FBG sensors measured during curing under vacuum at RT of CFRP laminate produced by VI

Resin Infusion of laminate with FBG containing OF and data acquisition set up

Conclusions

- Although resin pockets were observed in the laminates around the OF, they do not seem to influence the mechanical properties, when comparing the neat laminate with laminates with OF
- Wavelength change of FBG sensors show what seems to be the exothermic peak of curing but the resin is not solid right after that, as it typically happens in standard test methods for determination of gel time and peak exothermic temperature
- Low velocity impact tests will be further used to assess whether FBG sensors can detect BVID

References

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